

Towards Robust Detection of AI-Generated Text and Image Using Language and Vision Neural Models

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ABSTRACT:

AI-generated text and image detection has become an increasingly important field of research due to the rapid increase in machine-generated content across various platforms. With the advent of advanced language models such as GPT and image generation models like GANs and Diffusion Models (DMs), generating highly realistic and human-like content has become a reality. However, this progress has also raised concerns about the misuse of AI-generated content for malicious purposes, including the spread of fake images, misinformation and spam. Therefore, effective detection methods for AI-generated content are essential in order to reduce the potential risks posed by its misuse. This paper explores and proposes robust techniques for identifying AI-generated text and images. The approach involves leveraging the perplexity score and a learned binary classifier for text analysis. Similarly, image detection employs a large pre-trained vision language model to extract image features and uses an Artificial Neural Network to analyze those features for classification. The proposed approach achieves performance that is comparable to, and in many cases surpasses, existing methods across the majority of the public benchmark datasets for image detection, demonstrating effectiveness for both in-distribution and out-of-distribution images. This paper contributes to the field of AI ethics and security by providing an effective solution for identifying AI-generated text and images, thereby promoting trust, transparency and accountability in online content.

Keywords: ANN, CLIP, DM, GAN, GPT, Perplexity, VLM.

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INTRODUCTION

The rapid advancement of generative AI has drastically simplified the creation of realistic-looking text and images. The zero-shot generalization capability of large language models (LLMs) and image generation models enables them to be applied across diverse domains without the necessity for domain-specific training. Generative AI finds applications in a wide range of areas, including language translation [1], text classification [2] and, notably, image and text generation [3-6]. However, as AI models become increasingly advanced and capable of producing human-like textual

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and photographic content, concerns regarding the misuse of AI have become more prominent. While AI can facilitate a plethora of beneficial and lawful activities, it can also be exploited to generate misinformation, fake news, fraudulent product reviews and other ethically challenging content. Such misuse can, in some cases, even infringe upon individuals' intellectual property rights. Therefore, detecting AI-generated textual and photographic content has become increasingly important to ensure the responsible use of generative AI and to foster greater trust in AI among users.

AI-generated text and images often exhibit distinctive patterns associated with their respective generative models, which are typically imperceptible to the human eye but can be leveraged through forensic analysis to determine whether content is human-created or AI-generated. Chakraborty et al. [7] demonstrate the potential for AI-generated text detection and note that this task becomes increasingly difficult as the distribution of AI-generated text more closely resembles that of human-written text, necessitating larger sample sizes to maintain high detection accuracy. Recent research on AI-generated text detection has employed approaches such as watermarking [8], training binary classifiers [9-12] and using statistical metrics like perplexity scores [13,14]. While watermarking-based methods have shown some promise, they have limited practical use because their effectiveness relies on universal adoption by major LLM providers. Classifier-based approaches leveraging RoBERTa [15] have gained significant traction in synthetic text detection due to RoBERTa's demonstrated effectiveness in this domain. DetectGPT [14] shows that AI-generated text tends to occupy regions of negative curvature in the log-probability curve, whereas human-written text does not follow this pattern. The authors, thus, leverage this observation to construct an AI-generated text detector.

Traditional research on AI-generated image detection focused on visual anomalies such as irregular shadows or incorrect perspectives [16] and asymmetrical faces [17]. As synthetic images became more realistic to the human eye, researchers began employing complex deep learning-based methods that analyze spatial features [18-22] and frequency domain features [23-28] of images. More recently, the field has shifted toward the generalizable detection of out-of-distribution images using the feature space of large pre-trained vision language models, such as CLIP [29]. These methods aim to identify images generated by previously unseen models, even when the detectors are trained on data from a specific model [30,31].

In this work, we focus on training detectors for AI-generated text and images. For AI-generated text detection, we employ a perplexity score-based approach and a RoBERTa-based classifier and observe that the latter yields superior results. For AI-generated image detection, we train a neural network on the feature space extracted from CLIP and demonstrate its generalizability to models not encountered during training. Through our research, we show the feasibility of detecting both AI-generated text and images.

Our main contributions are summarized as follows:

1. We develop AI-generated image detectors that are comparable to, and in some cases better than, existing approaches, achieving an F1 score of up to 99.97% on in-distribution images and up to 92.42% on out-of-distribution images.
2. We develop AI-generated text detectors using the two best-performing methods and compare their effectiveness.
3. We develop an end-to-end AI-generated text and image detection system, provided as a web application, with the code made publicly available at: <https://github.com/rajendrabaskota/unmasking-the-creator>

RELATED WORKS

AI-Generated Text Detection

Watermark-based Approach

Watermarking in LLM involves inserting specific patterns into LLM-generated text in a way that is unnoticeable to humans, enabling later detection. This approach is inspired by earlier rule-based

techniques for watermarking language through syntax tree manipulation [32,33]. Kirchenbauer et al. [8] introduced an effective watermarking technique for LLMs that utilizes the logits produced by LLM at each step of text generation. Their soft watermarking technique divides tokens into “green” and “red” lists to encode watermark patterns. During response generation, the LLM selects tokens from the green list with higher probability. During the detection process, the same information is leveraged to flag texts containing a significant number of green-list tokens as AI-generated. Although the watermarking technique proposed by the author achieves a true positive rate of 99.8% and a false positive rate of only 1%, its practical applicability is limited. Deploying this approach in the real world would require integration with major LLMs and the LLM providers would need to disclose their models’ internal details to third parties for watermark detection.

Classifier-based Approach

The classifier-based approach has become a common technique for AI-generated text detection, where an ML model is trained to classify a given text as either AI-generated or human-authored. Solaiman et al. [9] trained a RoBERTa-based detector to differentiate between GPT-2-generated and human-written text. Numerous studies have focused on classifier-based natural language detection tasks. One of them is fake news and misinformation detection as proposed in [7]. OpenAI, too, trained a GPT-based model incorporating data from 34 language models as well as human-authored texts to detect AI-generated textual content [10]. RoBERTa [15] has gained popularity within the research community for AI-generated text detection and has already demonstrated its effectiveness in this domain [9-12].

Statistical Metrics-based Approach

Statistical metrics such as perplexity, model’s log probability and entropy have been used to differentiate between AI-generated and human-written text. HowkGPT [13] utilizes perplexity scores to classify whether a homework assignment was generated by ChatGPT or written by a student, achieving an F1 score of approximately 80% on a dataset containing all assignment categories and about 85% when math and coding assignments were excluded. HowkGPT shows the lowest accuracy in the math and coding categories, as answers in these domains are often similar across authors due to the objective nature of the questions and the fixed rules used to derive solutions. DetectGPT [14] is based on the observation that minor rewrites of AI-generated text exhibit lower log probabilities than the original model output, whereas minor rewrites of human-written text may have either higher or lower log probabilities. However, DetectGPT requires white-box access to the source model to achieve optimal results, which presents a significant limitation as most top-performing models are closed-source.

AI-Generated Image Detection

Traditional Methods

Images manipulated using traditional methods can often be detected with techniques that focus on specific image features, such as identifying scaling or rotation [34], compression artifacts [35] or inconsistent reflections [36]. Visual anomalies such as irregular shadows or incorrect perspectives [16] and asymmetrical faces [17] have also been used to detect synthetic images. However, these types of errors typically do not appear in images generated by modern text-to-image models, limiting the effectiveness of traditional detection approaches.

Methods based on Spatial Features

Although synthetic images often appear realistic to the human eye, they retain certain features from their generation models that enable detection [37-38]. Complex deep learning-based methods [18], [19] can also be employed to identify the digital patterns left by image generation models. To enhance the generalizability of detectors to domains not represented in the training set, researchers have utilized noise residuals instead of original images [20], focused on local patches [21] and explored combinations of local and global spatial features [22].

Methods based on Frequency Domain

GAN-generated images often exhibit regular patterns and high peaks in the frequency domain due to the up-sampling operations performed during image generation [23-25]. Although newer GAN

architectures, such as StyleGAN3 [26], reduce these peaks in the frequency domain, noticeable patterns between real and GAN-generated images still persist, particularly in the medium to high frequency ranges. Similar observations in the frequency domain have also been reported for images generated by Diffusion Models (DMs) [27,28]. However, the frequency spectrum features of images are easily affected by resizing, compression or deliberate manipulations aimed at removing generator traces [39-41].

Use of Large Pre-trained Vision Language Models

Large pre-trained Vision Language Models (VLMs), such as CLIP [29], have recently been used extensively for synthetic image detection, particularly in out-of-distribution scenarios. Ojha et al. [30] utilize the CLIP feature space of images and train synthetic image detectors on these feature representations using both nearest neighbor and feed-forward neural network-based binary classifiers. The detector trained by them performs comparably to previous techniques in in-distribution scenarios but outperforms them in out-of-distribution detection, achieving improvements of +15.07 mean Average Precision (mAP) and +25.90% accuracy. Similarly, Cozzolino et al. [31] employ the same approach as Ojha et al. [30], but use a Support Vector Machine (SVM)-based classifier instead of a nearest neighbor or neural network-based classifier.

METHODOLOGY

AI-Generated Text Detection

This section provides a detailed overview of the dataset, methodologies and system architecture employed for AI-generated text detection in this project. Two methods, perplexity score-based classification and learning-based binary classification, were used and are further described in the subsequent sections. Additionally, client-side and server-side web applications were developed to facilitate the easy use of trained models as shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1. System Block Diagram for AI-generated Text Detection

Data Preparation

The HC3-English [42] and GPT Wiki Intro [43] datasets are used for this project. They contain human-written text and their corresponding AI-generated versions. The HC3-English dataset comprises 24,300 questions, each paired with answers from both humans and ChatGPT. The GPT Wiki Intro dataset consists of 150,000 Wikipedia articles, along with their corresponding AI-generated versions and the prompts used for their generation. In total, this project collects 348,600 data samples for training AI-generated text detectors. The data samples are divided into training and testing sets, with the training set containing 95% of the total data.

Perplexity Score Method

Figure 2. AI-generated Text Detection using Perplexity Score Method

We leverage perplexity scores to distinguish AI-generated texts from the real ones. Perplexity is commonly used during the training and evaluation of language models. During training, the model aims to minimize perplexity, effectively maximizing the likelihood of generating the training data. In evaluation, perplexity serves as a quantitative metric to compare different language models and assess their performance in generating coherent and meaningful text. A low perplexity value suggests that the language model can make more informed predictions and is better at capturing the patterns and relationships within the language data. Conversely, a high perplexity value indicates that the model is uncertain about the next word and might not fully understand the language's syntax and semantics. An AI-generated text usually has a lower perplexity score than a human-written text. Therefore, a perplexity threshold can be used to distinguish between the two. The texts with perplexity scores below the threshold are classified as AI-generated, while those above it are classified as human-written. The perplexity of the sequence $X = \{x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n\}$ can be mathematically expressed through the following function:

$$\text{Perplexity}(X) = \exp \left\{ -\frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n \log p_{\theta} (x_i | x_{<i}) \right\} \quad (1)$$

where $\text{Perplexity}(X)$ measures how well a probabilistic model predicts the next token in the sequence, x_i is the i th token in sequence X , $x_{<i}$ are all the preceding tokens and n is the number of tokens in the sequence.

Given a text with n number of tokens, a sliding window-based approach is used to calculate the perplexity score. Since models like GPT-2 can only process 1024 tokens at once, we use a sliding window to incorporate longer sequences. A sliding window comprises m number of tokens at a step, m being the window size. The window is slid with a stride size of k , where $k < m$. The stride size of $k < m$ allows the model to have a large context at each step since there will be at least $m - k$ number of preceding tokens as the context for the next prediction. Furthermore, we have chosen a window

size of 64, which is far smaller than the context window of GPT-2. This was done in order to reduce the memory usage during training and inference. Table 1 presents the hyperparameter tuning metrics for the perplexity score method, where the window size of 64 and the stride of 32 are selected based on the F1 score. Each step of the sliding window computes the negative log likelihood loss using GPT-2. The losses from all the steps are then averaged and exponentiated to compute the perplexity score for the whole sequence as represented by Equation 1.

Table 1. Hyperparameter Tuning for Perplexity Score Method

S.N.	Window Size	Stride	Best Perplexity Threshold	F1 Score
1	32	16	17.1	0.9036
2	64	32	12.8	0.9071
3	128	64	11.2	0.8942

The obtained perplexity score is then compared against the predetermined perplexity threshold to classify the given text as AI-generated or human-written. To determine the perplexity threshold, the ROC curve, which represents the relationship between True Positive Rate (TPR) and False Positive Rate (FPR), is generated on the training set for various thresholds, and the corresponding AUC (Area Under the Curve) is calculated. The threshold that gives the highest AUC score is selected as the best threshold to be used during inference.

Learning-based Binary Classification Method

In addition to the perplexity score method, we also train a binary classifier for detecting AI-generated texts. We use RoBERTa [15] as a base model for binary classification which is further fine-tuned on our training dataset. The effectiveness of RoBERTa for AI-generated text detection has already been demonstrated in previous works [9], [11], [12] and was found to be better than BERT in [44] for the same task. The RoBERTa model used in this paper uses the GeLU [45] activation function, the AdamW [46] optimizer with a weight decay of 0.01, learning rate of 5×10^{-5} , batch size of 16, classification layer dropout of 0.1 and binary cross entropy (BCE) as the loss function. Mathematically, the BCE loss between the predicted probability p and the true label y is given by:

$$BCE(y, p) = -[y \log(p) + (1 - y) \log(1 - p)] \quad (2)$$

Before training the RoBERTa model, the data samples are tokenized and labeled, with 1 for AI-generated text and 0 for human-written text. The dataset is then split into training and testing sets in a 95% to 5% ratio, as shown in Figure 1.

AI-GENERATED IMAGE DETECTION

Analysis of Image Generated by GAN and Diffusion Models

Figure 3. Real Image (Left) and its Magnitude Spectrum (Right)

Figure 4. GAN-generated Image (Left) and its Magnitude Spectrum (Right)

The magnitude spectrum, generated using the Discrete Fourier Transform (DFT), of the real image (Figure 3) depicts the absence of high-frequency components in the image. In other words, there is no abrupt change in pixel magnitude in real images. In contrast, the spectrum of the GAN-generated image (Figure 4) reveals several artifacts, introducing noise to the generated image. These artifacts are absent in the real image, resulting in a cleaner and clearer appearance. This shows that there are some discrepancies in the frequency spectra of real and GAN-generated images, which can be exploited to classify between the two.

Figure 5. Real Image (Left) and its Magnitude Spectrum (Right)

Figure 6. Diffusion-generated Image (Left) and its Magnitude Spectrum (Right)

The comparison of the magnitude spectra of the real image (Figure 5) and its corresponding fake image generated using a diffusion model (Figure 6) shows that the differences are extremely subtle and hard to notice. This implies that the classification between real and diffusion-generated fake images is difficult on the basis of frequency components. On the contrary, this discrepancy in the GAN-generated images is huge. This project, therefore, goes beyond frequency comparison with the aim of building a more robust detection framework.

Architecture for AI-generated Image Detection

This project utilizes a pretrained CLIP model to extract unbiased features from images for the

detection of AI-generated images. CLIP (Contrastive Language-Image Pre-training) was trained on a large corpus of image-text pairs to associate images with their corresponding descriptions. Since it was not specifically trained for real-vs-fake classification, the features it extracts are task-independent and free from bias toward either class.

Figure 7. Architecture for AI-generated Image Detection

Given an input image, we employ the CLIP:ViT-L/14 model to extract image embeddings of dimension 768. Those embeddings are used as features to train a neural network for the task of binary classification, as shown in Figure 7.

Visualization of Feature Space Extracted from CLIP

Figure 8. t-SNE visualization of real and fake images generated using GAN (left) and Diffusion (right) models. The red dots denote fake images.

Figure 8 shows the t-SNE visualization of features for real images (yellow) and their corresponding fake counterparts (red) generated using ProGAN (left) and ADM (right) models. The features used for the generation of t-SNE are obtained from CLIP:ViT-L/14, which provides the embedding of dimension 768. The above figure depicts a clear separation between real and GAN-generated images, while showing high overlap between the features of real and diffusion-generated images. This implies that diffusion models can generate more realistic images than GANs. Importantly, this also suggests that the detection of diffusion-generated images is inherently more challenging than the detection of GAN-generated images.

Data Preparation

The dataset for training the AI-generated image detection model consists of real images and their

AI-generated counterparts, produced using Generative Adversarial Networks (GANs) and diffusion models. The GAN dataset comprises images from various GAN models like ProGAN, StarGAN, StyleGAN, StyleGAN2, BigGAN and GauGAN. Similarly, the diffusion dataset includes images generated by Glide-100-27, LDM 200, DALL-E, Glide-50-27, LDM-100, LDM-200-CFG, Glide-100-10 and Guided Diffusion. Additional datasets include images from whichfaceisreal, deepfake, SAN, CRN, IMLE and seeingdark models.

Table 2. Number of GAN, Diffusion and Other Model Images in the Test Set

Model	Type	Number of Images
ProGAN	GAN	8000
BigGAN	GAN	4000
StarGAN	GAN	3998
GauGAN	GAN	10000
StyleGAN	GAN	11982
StyleGAN2	GAN	15976
Glide_100_27	Diffusion	1000
LDM_200	Diffusion	1000
Guided	Diffusion	1000
DALL-E	Diffusion	1000
Glide_50_27	Diffusion	1000
LDM_100	Diffusion	1000
LDM_200_cfg	Diffusion	1000
Glide_100_10	Diffusion	1000
deepfake	Other	5405
whichfaceisreal	Other	2000
SAN	Other	438
CRN	Other	12764
IMLE	Other	12764
seeingdark	Other	360

Training Binary Classifier

Three sets of experiments were conducted by varying the training dataset. In the first setting, the model was trained only on ProGAN images; in the second, it was trained on ADM (Ablated Diffusion Model) [47] images; and in the third, it was trained on a combination of both ProGAN and ADM images. ADM is a variant of the diffusion model and the images generated by it have a different distribution from those produced by GANs. In the first and the second settings, while the model was trained solely on ProGAN and ADM images, respectively, images from other models were included in the testing set to evaluate the generalizability of the trained model to unseen image sources. For the first experiment, 720k images (360k ProGAN-generated and 360k real) were used for training. For the second experiment, which involved diffusion images, 40k ADM-generated and 40k real images were used.

The training process utilizes the image embeddings extracted using CLIP:ViT-L/14. Before feature extraction from CLIP, the images undergo preprocessing steps, such as resizing to fit CLIP's input layer and channel verification, to ensure consistency and compatibility for subsequent training. The hyperparameters used for training the models are shown in Table 3. Since neural networks without hidden units and dropout produced the best results for ADM and the combination of ProGAN and ADM datasets, those fields are left blank in Table 3. During testing or inference, embeddings are generated from the images using the same CLIP model. The image embeddings are then fed into the trained neural network to predict their labels.

Table 3. Hyperparameters for Neural Network-based Image Embedding Classification

Dataset	Hidden Units	Epochs	Learning Rate	Dropout
ProGAN	100	2,500	0.03	0.2
ADM	-	3,000	0.03	-
ProGAN + ADM	-	20,000	0.3	-

RESULTS

In this section, we present and discuss the performance metrics of our AI-generated text and image detectors during both training and testing.

Evaluation Metrics

Precision

Precision measures the accuracy of positive predictions made by a model and thus indicates the proportion of correctly predicted positive instances out of all instances predicted as positive. In other words, precision measures the model's ability to avoid false positives. A high precision score suggests that when the model predicts a positive outcome, it is likely to be correct. This metric is crucial in situations where the cost of false positive errors is high.

$$\text{Precision} = \frac{\text{True Positive}}{\text{True Positive} + \text{False Positive}} \quad (3)$$

Recall

Recall, also called sensitivity or the True Positive Rate (TPR), describes how well a classification model can identify all the positive cases in a dataset. In other words, it measures the proportion of actual positive instances that the model correctly identifies. Recall is calculated by dividing the number of true positive predictions (correctly identified positive cases) by the total number of actual positive instances in the data. A high recall means the model successfully detects most positive cases, reducing the number of false negatives (positive cases that were missed).

$$\text{Recall} = \frac{\text{True Positive}}{\text{True Positive} + \text{False Negative}} \quad (4)$$

F1 Score

The F1 score is a metric that combines both precision and recall into a single value, providing a balanced evaluation of a classification model's performance. It is particularly useful in situations where the class distribution is imbalanced, meaning one class significantly outnumbers the other, as it considers both false positives and false negatives. The F1 score is calculated as the harmonic mean of precision and recall, giving equal weight to both metrics. The F1 score will be high only if both precision and recall are high, making it a useful metric for tasks where false positives and false negatives have different costs or implications. F1 score is given by:

$$\text{F1 Score} = \frac{2 \times \text{Precision} \times \text{Recall}}{\text{Precision} + \text{Recall}} \quad (5)$$

AUC-ROC (Area Under the Receiver Operating Characteristic Curve)

The ROC (Receiver Operating Characteristic) curve is a plot of True Positive Rate vs. False Positive Rate at different classification thresholds and AUC-ROC (Area Under the ROC Curve) measures the entire area under the ROC curve, ranging from 0 to 1. An AUC-ROC of 1 represents a perfect classifier, while an AUC-ROC of 0.5 indicates a classifier with no discriminative ability, equivalent to random guessing.

AI-generated Text Detection

Two experiments were conducted for detecting AI-generated text. The first experiment used a

perplexity score threshold to distinguish real text from AI-generated counterparts, while the second experiment involved training a RoBERTa model for binary classification.

Figure 9 shows the histogram plot for AI-generated and human-written text samples for the full dataset, which contains 174,000 samples for each of the two classes. As expected, the histogram plot for AI-generated texts peaks at a lower perplexity value than human-crafted texts. The region of overlap between the two histograms can introduce some error in the prediction, but the overlap seems to be small compared to the area of the histograms. Overall, the results are strong, as the two histograms are clearly separated. The tail of the histogram for human-written text extends to higher perplexity values, whereas the tail for AI-generated text is comparatively shorter.

Figure 9. Histogram of Perplexity Score Count on Full Training Dataset

Figure 10. Perplexity Threshold vs. AUC and F1 Score

Figure 10 shows the plots of AUC-ROC and F1 score for various perplexity score thresholds on the training set. We can see that both curves have a single peak value and the corresponding perplexity value is chosen as the threshold value for testing and inference. The peak values of both the AUC and F1 score curves appear to align closely. However, the AUC vs. Perplexity Threshold curve is used to determine the optimal threshold in this project. We can see that the highest AUC score of 0.9080 is achieved at the perplexity threshold of 12.80 in the training dataset. When this threshold is applied to the testing set, it yields an F1 score of 90.67% as shown in Table 4.

Table 4. Perplexity Method Metrics in Full Dataset

Metric	Value
Best AUC-ROC	0.9080
Perplexity threshold on best AUC-ROC	12.80
F1 score of the test dataset	90.67%

The perplexity score ranges from 9.80 to 14.80, while the F1 score ranges from 89.74% to 99.57%, depending on the text domain and length, as presented in Table 5. A common pattern observed is that fact-based or non-subjective domains, such as finance and medicine, tend to have clearer separation of histograms of the two classes, resulting in higher F1 scores. In contrast, subjective domains show greater overlap, leading to lower performance. Furthermore, datasets grouped by text length tend to have more similar perplexity thresholds and F1 scores than those grouped by domain.

Table 5. Metrics of Perplexity Method on Different Datasets

Dataset Type	Best Perplexity Threshold	F1 Score on Test Set
Full (GPT-Wiki-Intro + HC3)	12.80	90.67%
GPT-Wiki-Intro	12.90	90.41%
HC3	12.60	92.42%

HC3 - Reddit ELI5	14.80	91.75%
HC3 - Open QA	9.80	90.32%
HC3 - Medicine	11.70	99.57%
HC3 - Finance	11.10	97.25%
HC3 - Wiki CSAI	11.30	90.24%
Text length >= 250 Characters	12.80	91.57%
Text length >= 500 Characters	12.40	91.79%
Text length >= 1000 Characters	12.20	89.74%

In addition to the perplexity score method, a RoBERTa-based binary classification model was trained for 2500 steps for AI-generated text detection. Table 6 shows the comparison between the perplexity score method and the RoBERTa-based method. We can see that the RoBERTa-based binary classification method performed better than the perplexity score-based method.

Table 6. Comparison between Perplexity Score Method and RoBERTa-based Classifier

Method	F1 Score
Perplexity Score	90.67%
RoBERTa	98.81%

AI-generated Image Detection

Three experiments were conducted for AI-generated image detection on the available datasets. The first experiment used ProGAN-generated images for training, the second used ADM-generated images and the third combined both ProGAN and ADM datasets. The generalization ability of the trained models was assessed by testing them on images from 20 different GAN and diffusion models.

Table 7 and Table 8 represent the comparison between different methods of detecting real/fake images based on the accuracy score and the F1 score, respectively. The scores for previous two literature, Ojha et al. [30] and Cozzolino et al. [31], were computed using the respective trained model weights provided by the authors. We can see that the model trained solely on ProGAN dataset is able to generalize across other unseen GANs. Contrary to the performance obtained on GAN images, the model slightly struggles to classify diffusion-generated images. This is because of the fact that the architecture of GANs and diffusion models are completely different and so are the generated images. However, our model trained only on ProGAN shows **+14.89%** improvement in accuracy and **+9.75%** improvement in F1 score as compared to the previous approach. We can also see that the metrics obtained by our model are comparable, if not better, across all the datasets as compared to the previous approaches. The model trained jointly on ProGAN and ADM datasets seems to capture the nuances of both GAN and Diffusion images effectively, providing effective performance across both GAN and diffusion images. Its performance on GAN-generated images is comparable to that of the model trained solely on ProGAN images, whereas its performance on diffusion-generated images surpasses that of the model trained solely on the ADM dataset.

Table 7. Comparison between Different Methods for Detecting Real/Fake Images in terms of Accuracy Score

Dataset	Dataset Type	Detection Method				
		Ojha et al. [30]	Cozzolino et al. [31]	Ours		
				ProGAN	ADM	ProGAN + ADM
BigGAN	GAN	0.949	0.74	0.9555	0.7845	0.8282
StarGAN	GAN	0.96	0.55	0.9559	0.8084	0.9552
GauGAN	GAN	0.998	0.84	0.9573	0.8849	0.8956
StyleGAN	GAN	0.84	0.7	0.8893	0.8128	0.9539
StyleGAN2	GAN	0.753	0.71	0.8293	0.8227	0.9342
ProGAN	GAN	0.9995	0.73	0.9997	0.8946	0.9992
Glide_100_27	Diffusion	0.785	0.87	0.8975	0.9475	0.9515
LDM_100	Diffusion	0.95	0.89	0.879	0.9375	0.9465
LDM_200	Diffusion	0.944	0.89	0.8905	0.938	0.944

LDM_200_cfg	Diffusion	0.74	0.89	0.9245	0.8215	0.838
Guided	Diffusion	0.6965	0.84	0.918	0.886	0.8815
DALL-E	Diffusion	0.873	0.89	0.7655	0.891	0.931
Glide_50_27	Diffusion	0.7905	0.87	0.677	0.947	0.955
Glide_100_10	Diffusion	0.779	0.87	0.874	0.947	0.9565
seeingdark	Other	0.59	0.7	0.775	0.5888	0.5833
CRN	Other	0.573	0.53	0.9873	0.6445	0.6402
SAN	Other	0.565	0.78	0.9352	0.5753	0.5639
IMLE	Other	0.6885	0.54	0.6095	0.6615	0.6405
deepfake	Other	0.681	0.51	0.7296	0.5348	0.7110
whichfaceisreal	Other	0.869	0.711	0.892	0.6395	0.7515
Average		0.8012	0.7526	0.8671	0.7984	0.843

Table 8. Comparison between Different Methods for Detecting Real/Fake Images in terms of F1 Score

Dataset	Dataset Type	Detection Method				
		Ojha et al. [30]	Cozzolino et al. [31]	Ours		
				ProGAN	ADM	ProGAN + ADM
BigGAN	GAN	0.9473	0.833	0.9554	0.7756	0.8231
StarGAN	GAN	0.9609	0.721	0.9559	0.8015	0.9551
GauGAN	GAN	0.998	0.922	0.9572	0.8838	0.8944
StyleGAN	GAN	0.8107	0.849	0.8880	0.8125	0.9538
StyleGAN2	GAN	0.6733	0.805	0.8244	0.8227	0.9340
ProGAN	GAN	0.9995	0.862	0.9997	0.8939	0.9992
Glide_100_27	Diffusion	0.7302	0.882	0.8968	0.9473	0.9514
LDM_100	Diffusion	0.948	0.9	0.8778	0.9374	0.9464
LDM_200	Diffusion	0.9414	0.9	0.8896	0.9379	0.9439
LDM_200_cfg	Diffusion	0.6543	0.898	0.9242	0.8203	0.8370
Guided	Diffusion	0.5851	0.827	0.9177	0.884	0.8800
DALL-E	Diffusion	0.8565	0.897	0.7544	0.8909	0.9309
Glide_50_27	Diffusion	0.7389	0.876	0.6522	0.9468	0.9549
Glide_100_10	Diffusion	0.7206	0.884	0.8726	0.9468	0.9564
seeingdark	Other	0.6372	0.592	0.7747	0.5180	0.5186
CRN	Other	0.2561	0.398	0.9873	0.6086	0.5870
SAN	Other	0.281	0.718	0.9351	0.5519	0.5500
IMLE	Other	0.5482	0.509	0.6013	0.6229	0.5872
deepfake	Other	0.5683	0.68	0.7178	0.4247	0.7035
whichfaceisreal	Other	0.8531	0.612	0.8917	0.6260	0.7386
Average		0.7215	0.7783	0.8637	0.7827	0.8323

CONCLUSION

In this paper, we presented multiple detectors for identifying AI-generated text and images by leveraging robust existing methods and introducing meaningful enhancements. For AI-generated text detection, we explored two prominent approaches: a perplexity score-based method and a learning-based binary classification method and also compared their effectiveness. For AI-generated image detection, we utilized the feature space of a large pre-trained vision-language model and trained separate models on three different datasets to empirically demonstrate the generalizability of our approach. Our image detector achieved comparable, if not better, performance than existing methods on most in-distribution and out-of-distribution datasets. We hope that our work will promote the responsible use of generative AI and help mitigate the spread of ethically challenging content. Future work should focus more on improving the interpretability of detection methods and developing even more generalizable approaches for identifying AI-generated content.

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